

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

HISTORICAL CHOICES OF GEORGIA AND MODERN GLOBAL TRENDS

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Abstract

"I love the past of Georgia ... the background of its life is Georgian polyphony. This one voice and this - many voices that are looking for something, by which they understand each other. Georgian polyphony is the background of its spirituality, so to speak.

Why do I love Georgia? I love Georgia because in the course of our history there were people who performed personal acts and rose above the ethnos. An ethnos is inert, but it becomes a nation when the representatives of that nation become individuals in an effort to think independently. Faced with the challenge of history, such individuals willingly stand together and then create a nation together.....(Merab Mamardashvili).

Keywords: Georgia, Christian civilization, modern world, global trends

Introduction

An adult conscious person chooses consciously or passively to cross the paths of life. Accordingly, his consciousness is formed and his place in life becomes clear: where he is and where he wants to be. In this process, it is natural to ask questions: what is happening in the world today? Where and in relation to whom does man stand himself and humanity with its cognitive potential? What does he want and why? And finally, what influences him materially or spiritually?

In general, language is capable of a lot of things, it carries a lot of content, both from a worldview and psychological point of view.

Words just don't form. "Minute world" in this is a worldview, a position, a vision in relation to the world and the givenness of human life according to time.

We live in a media-created reality, which is the greatest tragedy of modern times. According to Jean Baudrard, we are in the reality created by the media, in the world of "simulations and simulacra", where one is the objective reality in which the world, humanity, and specifically Georgianness exists, and the other is the reality created by the media, the media, which you cannot touch, but it touches you. In a sense, it touches you and digs into your soul, you are literally there, you live there, and this life is absolutely what it is not, and where is it? In your psyche, having taken the place of your critical consciousness, it has been pushed aside and presented to you as your captor. Humanity today is in the reality of the Platonic "myth of the cave", which clearly proposed a new dimension of values and values, presented us in the form of an average arithmetical person, and used their appropriate study, characterization, and title on the principle of "the signifier of the void".

Confusion of values occurs in the modern world. There is room for ignoring behavioral patterns. Moving forward with technological progress proved dangerous for the world. In particular, it caused a cultural regression.

Globalization is an inevitable phenomenon, and it is connected with the development of scientific and

technical progress. It can be said that the whole world has become global, but this does not necessarily mean that large countries should absorb the cultural, spiritual, or national values of small countries in order to create a single and faceless culture. Some people think that the spiritual or national values of small nations create conflict and confrontation, which may turn into enmity and strife. In fact, this is not the case at all, these values, their diversity, on the contrary, enrich the world.

Today, it is obvious that the earth has shrunk, it cannot experience its own dimensions. Spiritually exhausted, technically strengthened, the goal became strictly economic development. Where money is the goal, there is a deficiency in human thinking because all activities are related to it.

Man has a problem with the essence of his existence. Along with the counterfeiting of everything, everything is for sale. This is a tragedy, an epoch-making attack on culture. Mankind was put to the test by money, and he failed it, got stuck and fell out.

Today, in the 21st century, when integration processes are so active in the world, in order to ensure the maximum protection of human rights and create the best conditions for them, the problem of life is faced.

And human life is how to bring beauty, love, purity, truth, or healthy harmony here in this earthly existence. And today's man is tired, deceived, afraid.

Today, people have become poor with everything. Everyone and everything loses its essential signs, we shrink and love slips out of our hands. The most important thing for a person is the feeling of relationships and connections with others. Of course, this connection is very relevant today and "progressively" growing, but what are we connected to each other? With the dead, the decaying, the transitory, that which is pure materialized. Everything turned into forms, perceptions, not arguments. The world is at the point where all of this has to explode.

It is necessary to analyze the effect of the economic situation on a person. Being or possessing? How should a person manage these two in relation to each

other in time and space? How to dispose of one's material condition so as not to lose one's presence in this world, to become the servant of one's possessions.

Every era, every society tries to overcome the global problems in the world economy in its own way, but how?

Every time has its own characteristics. Our time differs from other times only in that the Gospel teaches us that by multiplying many iniquities, love is judged. Everything is measured by money. Even time is used as a measure of money. The modern economic slogan is: "Time is money", "Time is a means of making money", but the blessed Augustine defines time as follows: "For what is time, if not an equal, alternating and successive change, to which we all and the whole world are subjected by unconditional necessity". Therefore, if there is no creation, there is no changeable existence of creation, no change, and no time. Time always implies some duration, a process in which past, present and future can be distinguished. But the beginning, that is, the first instant in which the world was created, is indivisible. It has no place for any duration and is therefore beyond time. Time itself had its origin from the creation of the world, before which there was eternity. Time before us is unknown and still untouched. However, we also know that "the present born from the past is the parent of the future".

Today, Georgia stands at the crossroads of elections. We should restore the "horn of life" and give the nation "science of life".

The course of the country should be directed towards independence. Achieving independence is not easy. We judge on a national scale and the world judges on a geopolitical scale. In this difficult environment, we must protect ourselves from being surrounded by powerful countries and find a way to be independent. Let's give up the weapons of battle, which are suffering, slander, lies, fraud, aggression, accusations. Physical aggression gives rise to confrontation, resistance, and spiritual aggression corrupts and destroys the nation.

Independence brings peace, unity, reconstruction. This is the state in which we manifest our God-given talents in our own works.

The Lord richly rewarded us Georgians with creative talent and a sense of beauty.

We need independence, because there should be peace, our unity and for the Georgian nation to have its say in the diversity of world culture. Beauty is our inner expression when there is peace, unity, faith, God's grace and love. This is why we are fighting for independence, so that we can offer the Lord intelligent sacrifices, love and the talent with which he has so abundantly rewarded us, and thus our nation can appear before the world as a representative of the civilization that today is changing, breaking, and losing the true source of emotion by which people are governed.

The history of humanity is not static, it undergoes metamorphosis and does not develop only chronologically, it is characterized by internal development.

In the conditions of active globalization, which is fueled by geopolitical thinking, it is paradoxical that in a civilized democratic European family it is doubtful to

integrate the homeland of the "tiger" with both economic and social values, while Europe is neither a geographical location, nor a political decision, nor desires. Europeanness is European consciousness, and the latter is being in the highest instance of consciousness. Which means that you are entirely responsible for your own destiny, while Europe and the European consciousness is based on Greek culture and Christianity. So what's going on?

In the modern civilized world in the reality of Goethe's "Faust" today, "a great field for listeners" is unacceptable for "fit men" and "a country given to men with countless colors" is alien and marginal.

Humanity experiences nostalgia for the physical Christ and does not realize the longing and necessity of the spiritual Christ.

In a confused and confused world, culture and architecture are different. We see skyscrapers, outwardly linear, pragmatic and rational, where there is no love, beauty, harmony. There are only geometric lines, which are the fruit of the civilization of Cain, in the form of the construction of the Godly Babylon, which the Lord then dismantled. We also have modern architecture, but it cannot erase the old, because in the old there is a longing for heaven, but for the Lord, by the Lord, and there is the idea of Babylon, to make a name and reach to heaven. That is why the civilization of equality with God and the civilization of unity with God, i.e. Christian civilization, came into conflict with each other. It is time for the world to perceive the Georgian nation not only as a developing country, but also as one of the hubs of Christian civilization in the East.

Conclusion

According to biblical history, after we, the immortal people of heaven, refused to be eternal and did not fulfill the word of God, we still remained in the world, we did not disappear, simply, the complexity of body and soul was broken and the body became corruptible, and man became mortal... Now what is the essence of our life? on earth? Whoever fights for his life, his life is also in danger. The wheel spins, life weaves. One is followed by the other, the second and the third, the human race multiplies. Who knows what other biblical lines Adam and Eve will break and in which part of infinity will be transformed into a civilization? We must remember that there are two dimensions: 1. The dimension of the measure of Christian eternal life and 2. The dimension of this village, fleeting and built on conjecture, which unfortunately is actually today It is not in agreement.

Now it depends on us what we use that free will for. Today, in the modern era, humanity is struggling to be freed from God-given freedom and not exerting itself. Economic activity is carried out with sophisticated PR-technologies, which is written as a marketing strategy between the fruit of the paradise tree and "Apple" in time and space. So that the pleasure quotient of the society is satisfied as much as possible, and we forget the main thing, that man came to the world not for pleasure, but for happiness.

Thus, "the road from modernity to Orthodoxy and vice versa" is difficult, as Father Sergiy Bulgakov says, but it must be done.

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